

Development of a new copper(II) ion-selective PVC membrane electrode based on tris(2-benzimidazolylmethyl)amine

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Abstract : A new poly(vinylchloride) based membrane, containing a synthesized ligand tris(2-benzimidazolylmethyl)amine as a membrane carrier, was used to fabricate a copper(II)-selective electrode. The membrane having the composition of various components, 60% *o*-NPOE in the presence of 32% PVC, 5% ionophore and 3% NaTPB as an anion excluder exhibits a near Nernstian potential response of 29.3 ± 0.4 mV decade⁻¹ over a wide concentration range (1.0×10^{-8} to 1.0×10^{-2} M) with a detection limit of 7.2×10^{-8} between pH 2.5–8.5 with a fast response time (10 s). The selectivity coefficient values were determined by matched potential method (MPM), indicate excellent selectivity for Cu^{II} ions over a large number of mono-, di- and trivalent cations. The proposed electrode exhibits an adequate shelf life (~5 months) without any considerable divergence in potentials. It was successfully applied to the determination of copper in water samples of the river Yamuna collected at different sites of Delhi.

Keywords : Copper(II) ion-selective electrode, PVC membrane, potentiometry, tris(2-benzimidazolylmethyl)amine.

Introduction

Determination of copper assumes importance in view of its widespread occurrence in environmental samples. As such large concentration of copper can be tolerated by human being, however, excessive dosage and long term exposure may cause headache, stomachache, dizziness, vomiting and diarrhea, while high uptake of copper results Wilson disease¹. The determination of Cu²⁺ ions has been carried out directly or indirectly by a variety of classical and instrumental methods, including volumetric titrations, gravimetric detection², spectrophotometry³, inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES)⁴, anodic stripping voltammetry⁵, chromatography⁶, atomic absorption spectrometry⁷ are used for its determination at low concentration level. However, several sophisticated analytical techniques such as ICP-AES, X-ray fluorescence, HPLC, DDP, have been applied for the determination of trace amounts of copper. Many of these methods involve several time-consuming manipulations, expensive equipments, expert operators and much

space. Therefore, there is critical need for the development of selective, portable, inexpensive diagnostic tools for the determination of copper. Recently, the development of ion-selective electrodes (ISEs) are well established in most frequent application in the fields of environmental, agricultural, industrial and clinical analysis. This is due to their several advantages, such as high speed, ease of preparation, simple instrumentation, relatively fast response, wide working concentration range, adequate selectivity and low cost. These make ISE potentiometry very attractive for chemical and pharmaceutical analysis. Extensive efforts have been made to develop good sensitive electrode for copper ion⁸⁻¹⁴. In spite of availability of a number of Cu²⁺ selective electrode their use for Cu²⁺ estimation has been limited, because they show interference by K⁺, Ag⁺ and Fe³⁺ ions¹⁵⁻¹⁷, work over narrow concentration range^{18,19}, high response time¹⁹, show non-Nernstian response^{18,20,21}, and limited pH range²². In order to achieve wider applicability, the limitations need to be removed. Efforts in this direction are on using different materials for preparing of membranes.

Due to continuing efforts in this direction, we recently synthesized a highly copper selective electrode using an ionophore tris(2-benzimidazolylmethyl)amine, as a novel neutral carrier for the potentiometric monitoring of ultra-trace amounts of Cu^{2+} ion. This electrode is used due to high speed, wide concentration range, high detection limit, low cost, longer life time and perform better results as compared to Cu^{II} -selective electrodes reported earlier⁸⁻¹⁴. The results of this investigation are presented here.

Experimental

Reagents and equipments :

All the reagents used in this study were of analytical grade. Nitrilotriacetic acid and *o*-phenylene diamine were procured from Aldrich, USA, high molecular weight poly(vinylchloride) (PVC) (Fluka, Switzerland), benzyl acetate (BA), tri-*n*-butylphosphate (TBP), dioctylphthalate (DOP), *o*-nitrophenyloctyl ether (*o*-NPOE), *n*-butylacetate (NBA), sodiumtetraphenylborate (NaTPB) were obtained from Merck, Germany and used as received. The nitrate salt of all the cations were of analytical grade and used without any further purification except drying over P_4O_{10} . Solution of cationic salt 0.1 M was prepared in doubly distilled water. A Perkin-Elmer model 3100 atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) with a graphite furnace was used to determine the concentration of metal ion in the standard solutions.

Synthesis of tris(2-benzimidazolylmethyl)amine :

Nitrilotriacetic acid (1.91 g, 0.01 mol) and *o*-phenylenediamine (3.24 g, 0.03 mol) were finely ground and heated together at 190–200 °C using an oil bath. The reaction mixture was cooled and crushed. The powdered compound was refluxed in methanol containing decolorizing charcoal. On cooling pinkish white crystals were obtained which were filtered and dried in vacuum over P_4O_{10} . The chemical characterization of the synthesized compound was carried out by the spectroscopic methods. The results obtained were similar to those reported earlier³.

Electrode preparation :

The PVC based membranes were prepared according to a method reported by Craggs *et al.*²⁴. Varying amounts of the ionophore tris(2-benzimidazolylmethyl)amine, plasticizers as benzyl acetate (BA), tri-*n*-butylphosphate (TBP), dioctylphthalate (DOP), *o*-nitrophenyloctyl ether (*o*-NPOE), *n*-butylacetate (NBA), anion excluder sodium

tetraphenylborate (NaTPB) and poly(vinylchloride) (PVC) (as shown in Table 1) were dissolved in the minimum amount of tetrahydrofuran (THF). The solution was then allowed to evaporate for 24 h at room temperature to get transparent membrane of about 0.2 mm thickness. This was then cut to size and glued to one end of a Pyrex glass tube with araldite. The ratio of membrane ingredients, time of contact and concentration of equilibrating solution were optimized so that the membrane should be developed with stable potential.

Potential measurement :

The potential measurements were carried out with a digital potentiometer (Model 5652 A, ECIL, India) in conjugation with SCE as reference electrodes. The membranes were equilibrated with 1.0×10^{-2} M $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution for 2–3 days and the potential measurements were carried at 25 ± 0.1 °C using the following cell assembly :

External saturated calomel electrode (SCE)/internal solution 0.01 M $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ /membrane/test solution/internal saturated calomel electrode (SCE).

The concentration of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in the test solution was varied over the range of 1.0×10^{-8} to 1.0×10^{-2} M.

Sampling :

The river water of Yamuna was collected in April 2009, in high grade plastic bottles (2 L capacity) in triplicate and mixed to get a composite sample for each site. All the sample bottles were stored in ice boxes till brought to the laboratory for analysis. Five samples were taken from each site, which were homogenized and the composite samples were stored in high grade Teflon bottles.

Results and discussion

The free ionophore has four coordination sites due to the presence of nitrogen as donor atoms to form the metal chelate complexes. Ionophore used as electrode should have adequate complex formation constant and rapid exchange kinetics due to conformational changes between free ionophore and its metal complexes in the membrane. In addition to this the ionophore should be very soluble in the membrane matrix, and have a sufficient lipophilicity to prevent leaching from the membrane into the sample²⁵.

The ionophore was used as an ion selective electrode for a number of metal ions like alkaline earth metal ions, transition metal and heavy metal ions. Their potential responses and slopes were measured and shown in Fig. 1 and Table 1. It can be seen that the membrane based on

Table 1. Optimization and composition of membrane electrode (w/w)%

Sl. no.	PVC	Plasticizer	Ionophore	Excluder NaTPB	Slope (mV decade ⁻¹)	Response time (s)	Working concentration range (M)
1.	32	60 (BA)	0	8	18.5 ± 0.7	14	1 × 10 ⁻⁴ to 1 × 10 ⁻²
2.	33	61 (TBP)	4	2	20.5 ± 0.4	17	1 × 10 ⁻⁷ to 1 × 10 ⁻³
3.	33	58 (DOP)	3	6	22.8 ± 0.5	13	1 × 10 ⁻⁸ to 1 × 10 ⁻⁴
4.	32	60 (NPOE)	5	3	29.3 ± 0.4	10	1 × 10 ⁻⁸ to 1 × 10 ⁻²
5.	33	61 (NBA)	3	3	26.5 ± 0.6	16	1 × 10 ⁻⁵ to 1 × 10 ⁻³
6.	31	65 (DBP)	2	2	24.5 ± 0.5	15	1 × 10 ⁻⁶ to 1 × 10 ⁻³

Fig. 1. Potentiometric response curve of electrode for different cations.

tris(2-benzimidazolylmethyl)amine gives the best Nernstian response to the concentration of Cu^{II} in a wide concentration range.

Working concentration range and slope :

Before starting any experimentation, the membranes were equilibrated with 1.0 × 10⁻² M Cu^{II} solution. The experiments have shown that 2–3 days equilibration time is required for generating reproducible and stable potential. Different plasticizers and NaTPB were added to the membranes with the aim to improve the performance of the electrode. It is well known that the addition of plasticizers not only improves the work ability of the membranes, but also contributes significantly towards the improvement in the working concentration range, stability, linearity, sensitivity and life time of electrode^{26,27}. However, the selectivity remains usually unaffected and mainly depends on the metal-ionophore interaction. The plasticizer to be used in membranes should exhibit high lipophilicity, high molecular weight, low tendency for exudation from the polymer matrix, low vapor pressure and high capacity to dissolve the substrate and other ad-

ditives present in the membrane. Additionally, its viscosity and dielectric constant should be adequate²⁸. It should be noted that the presence of lipophilic anion in cation selective membrane electrodes not only diminishes the ohmic resistance²⁹, but also enhances the response. Thus five plasticizers namely BA, TBP, DOP, *o*-NPOE, NBA and anion excluder NaTPB were added in an attempt to improve the performance of electrode. For this purpose, the performance characteristics of several membranes having ingredients in the different preparations are listed in Table 1. Among these plasticizers, the use of 60% *o*-NPOE in the presence of 32% PVC, 5.0% ionophore and 3% NaTPB (membrane no. 4) gives the best sensitivity with a Nernstian slope of 29.3 ± 0.4 mV per decade in the concentration range of 1.0. The practical limit of detection was 7.2 × 10⁻⁸ M as determined from the intersection of the two extrapolated segments of the calibration graph based on recommended procedure by IUPAC^{30,31}. The overall optimized membrane potentiometric response characteristics have been summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of optimized copper ion-selective electrode

Properties of the electrode	Values
Type of electrode	Plasticized PVC membrane electrode
Optimum composition (w/w)%	5:3:60:32[I:NaTPB:o-NPOE:PVC]
Conditioning time and concentration	2-3 days, $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ $Cu(NO_3)_2$ solution
Linear working range	1.0×10^{-8} to $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$
Slope	9.3 ± 0.4 mV decade ⁻¹
pH	2.5-8.5
Detection limit	$7.2 \times 10^{-8} M$
Lifetime	~ 5 months
Response time	10 s
Storage	In $0.01 M$ $Cu(NO_3)_2$ with buffer solution at pH 5.0

Effect of internal solution :

The influence of the concentration of internal solution on the potential response of the polymeric electrode for Cu^{II} was studied. The concentration was varied from 1.0×10^{-2} to $1.0 \times 10^{-6} M$, and the potential response of electrode was observed. It was found that the best results in terms of slope and working concentration range has been obtained with internal solution of activity $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ concentration of $Cu(NO_3)_2$ solutions was quite appropriate for the smooth functioning of the proposed electrode.

Best pH range :

To study the influence of pH on the performance of

the electrode, the potential was studied by the use of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ of Cu^{2+} ions in the pH range of 1.5-10. To adjust the pH, very small volumes of concentrated NaOH or HCl were used. It was found that the electrode works best within the pH range 2.5-8.5, giving approximately constant potential reading, this can be taken as the working pH range of the electrode. The results are shown in Fig. 2. At lower pH value (2.5) a deviation in potential was observed, this is due to the response of the membrane to hydronium ion (protonation of nitrogen atoms in acidic media). At higher pH values (8.5), a decreasing in potential, due to the formation of insoluble of cupric hydroxide, was observed.

Dynamic response time and life time of electrode :

It is an important factor for any ion-selective electrode. According to IUPAC recommendation, the response time of the electrode is defined as the time between the additions of analyzing sample solution and the time when a limiting potential has been reached. In this study the practical response time of the proposed electrode was recorded by changing the concentration of copper ion in a series of solution, in the range of 1.0×10^{-6} to $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$. In the whole concentration range the electrode reaches its equilibrium response, very fast (10 s). The main factor responsible for the limited life time of electrode is believed to be the loss of one or more of its components while contacting with aqueous solutions. Sufficient lipophilicity of ionophore and plasticizers ensures stable potentials and long lifetimes. Among all the membranes prepared in this study, the lifetime of the electrode hav-

Fig. 2. The pH effect at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ Cu^{2+} ion solutions on the potential response of the electrode.

ing *o*-NPOE plasticizer was maximum and found to be ~5 months. During this period, the electrodes were used over extended period of time (one hour per day). After 5 months a slight gradual decreases in the slopes (from 29.3 ± 0.4 to 27.6 ± 0.5 mV per decade) was observed. However, it is important to emphasize that the membranes were stored in a 1.0×10^{-2} M Cu^{2+} solution when not in use.

Selectivity coefficient of proposed electrode :

The most important characteristics of any ISEs is its relative response to primary ion over other ions present in the solution which is expressed in terms of potentiometric selectivity coefficient $K_{A,B}^{\text{pot}}$ ³², which describes the preference of the membrane for an interfering ion as compared to Cu^{2+} ion. In this work, we determined selectivity coefficients with most widely used procedure match potential method (MPM)^{33,34}. According to the MPM, the selectivity coefficients are defined as the activity ratio of the primary ion (*A*) and the interfering ion (*B*) that gives the same potential change in a reference solution. Thus, one should measure the change in potential upon changing the primary ion activity. Then the interfering ion would be added to an identical reference solution until the same potential change is obtained. The selectivity coefficient $K_{A,B}^{\text{pot}}$ is determined as :

$$K_{A,B}^{\text{pot}} = \Delta A/a_B$$

where $\Delta A = (a'_A - a_A)$ that a_A is the initial primary activity of primary ion and a'_A the activity of *A* in the presence of interfering ion, *B*. If the value of selectivity coefficient is equal to 1.0 then it indicates that the electrode responds equally to primary as well as interfering ion. However, values smaller than 1.0 indicate that membrane electrode is responding more to primary ion than to interfering ions and in such a case the electrode said to be selective to primary ion over interfering ion. The concentra-

tion of Cu^{2+} in this study is 1.0×10^{-2} M. It is evident that electrode exhibits high performance for Cu^{2+} over a number of other cations used. The high selectivity of the membrane electrode for Cu^{2+} ion, most probably arise from strong tendency of the ionophore for the Cu^{2+} ions. The selectivity coefficient value are in the order of 1.0×10^{-2} or smaller indicating that the cations Cr^{3+} , Mg^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , NH_4^+ , Ca^{2+} and Ba^{2+} would not significantly disturb the electrode behavior. The selectivity coefficient of Ag^+ is in the order of 10.1, which may be due to the soft nature of metal ion. Hence, the electrode is sufficiently selective over the cations ions and can therefore be used to estimate copper in presence of cations by direct potentiometry.

Analytical application :

Analysis of Cu^{2+} ions in the water samples of river Yamuna :

The proposed Cu^{2+} ion-selective electrode was found to work well under the laboratory conditions. It was successfully applied to the determination of copper of the water samples collected from the various sites of river Yamuna in Delhi region. The analysis of river water samples does not require pretreatment except pH adjustment. The pH for all samples was adjusted at 4.0. The results observed for analysis were also compared with atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) analyzer. It is clear from the values in Table 3 that these were in a good agreement with the results obtained by AAS. Hence, the proposed electrode can be successfully employed for the estimation of Cu^{II} in waste water samples.

Conclusions :

The results obtained from the above mentioned study revealed that a potentiometric PVC based membrane containing a free ligand tris(2-benzimidazolylmethyl)amine as an ionophore with a *o*-NPOE as plasticizer and NaTPB as anion excluder in a ratio 5 : 3 : 60 : 32 [I : *o*-NaTPB :

Table 3. Analysis of Cu^{2+} ions by river water of Yamuna and by AAS

Sample no.	Name of place	pH found	pH after adjustment	Cu^{2+} concentration as determined by the electrode (ppm)	Cu^{2+} concentration as determined by AAS (ppm)
1	Ramghat	6.82	4.0	0.52 ± 0.02	0.53 ± 0.01
2	Soor Ghat	6.59	4.0	0.64 ± 0.03	0.67 ± 0.02
3	Laxmi Nagar	6.84	4.0	1.52 ± 0.05	1.54 ± 0.02
4	Okhla Bridge	7.19	4.0	1.57 ± 0.04	1.60 ± 0.03

NPOE : PVC] can be used for the determination of copper ions. The response time of the electrode is quite low and it could successfully be used for ~ 5 months without showing any significant drift in any of the response characteristics. The proposed electrode can be successfully employed to determine Cu^{II} quantitatively in the water samples of river Yamuna collected from different sites of Delhi.

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